

THE ROCKSONS FAMILY HOUSE CASE

Project background:

The Rocksons family house was a £2,300,000 new built residential property owned by Mr Adrian Rockson and located at No. 20 Creek Avenue, Kroll, within the Bellevue Conservation Area. The property consists six bedrooms, five receptions, a detached garden pavilion and was developed over a period of two and half years. When the property was completed on May 20, 2019, the project team breathed a sigh of relief. It all began when Mr Adrian Rockson, a developer, placed a call to Mr Jones Adams, his former Architect at Predios Architects on the morning of August 15, 2016 requesting for help with the development of a residential property. At the time of the request, Mr Rockson, who was familiar with the construction industry, was already developing eight residential blocks on the adjoining site to the Rocksons family house. Wanting to have a single point of contact and to avoid any stress regarding the project delivery, Mr Rockson requested for a design and build (D&B) arrangement and introduced Bay Consult, construction consultants, represented by Mr James Arthur, as his project manager (PM). However, this (i.e. D&B arrangement) was never realised as the design and implementation of the project eventually happened as the traditional procurement strategy.

Exhibit 1: The Rocksons family house near completion

This was because, the Designers, who were independent of the D&B Contractor were kept throughout the project by the Client to perform their design roles. Precisely, the design progressed deep into the construction phase and even though the lead design firm role (i.e. Architects/PDs) was novated to the D&B Contractor upon its appointment, the Contractor did

not have the capability to carry out the detailed designs (as expected by a D&B arrangement) so the Lead Designer was maintained for the design function.

The design process for the residential property commenced on August 22, 2016 when Mr Adams officially requested for a project brief from Mr Rockson. After two weeks, Mr Rockson submitted a brief, through Mr Arthur, to Mr Adams indicating the family requirements including bedroom spaces, welcoming areas, outdoor lounging areas, among others. The Client's initial project brief is indicated in Exhibit 2.

Exhibit 2: Client's initial brief

<p>Project Description & Aspirations The scheme consists of a new build family home for Adrian and Janet Rockson and their three children at No. 20 Creek Avenue, Kroll within the Bellevue Conservation Area.</p> <p>The Client's aspirations for their new home are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High quality, sustainable architecture, making the most of available resources • Flexibility and adaptability as the family grows up • Open and generous circulation space • Space for children to play and feel safe • Minimise 'wasted' space • Maximise use of natural light and natural ventilation • To have 6 bedrooms • To have 4-5 reception rooms • To be able to host large, informal parties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children bedrooms: possibly three, ability to naturally ventilate bedrooms and to black-out sunlight. • Guest bedrooms: possibly two, at least one of them to have en-suite bathroom. Guests to stay and feel comfortable yet separate. One room will probably host a future nanny. • Family bathroom: large and close to children bedrooms • Stand-alone WC rooms: one on ground floor and one on lower ground floor • Laundry room: with windows and linen cupboards • Pantry room: with sink and external door • Boot room: with storage for boots, coats, space for dog and external door • Entrance hall: to have storage space for hanging guests' coats
<p>Internal spatial requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kitchen: large and open, to enable at least two people to work at the same time • Dining area: connected to kitchen, to fit table for 12 people • Informal living area: close to kitchen/dining and playroom • Playroom: connected but separated from kitchen, ability to become a separate room in the future • Snug: contained room to watch TV, with fire place and bookcases • Drawing room: large, well-proportioned smart room with good views and large windows. Large fire place. Ability to host parties of 20 people. • Study: with desk, bookshelves and filing space. • Master bedroom: containing dressing room and en-suite bathroom 	<p>External spatial requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Garden: adapt the landscape of the garden to suit the family needs and host a one storey detached garden pavilion (approximately 320 sqft GIA) • Storage: for bikes and gardening tools • Shared forecourt: to improve the quality of the forecourt shared with No. 21 - 22 Creek Avenue with an appropriate landscape design and to increase parking provision and add a shared bin store

Client's General health and safety (H&S) Arrangements:

Mr Rockson appointed Mr Adams as the Principal Designer (PD) for the project. The scope of what the PD was supposed to do, specifically, on the project regarding H&S risk management was based on the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) form of contract and was not to go beyond that. Further, the contract of engagement as Designers (i.e. Architects) was separate from that of appointment as a PD. The PD was engaged throughout the project, right from the design stage to handover.

Since Mr Rockson had already started developing eight residential blocks on the adjacent site, he therefore appointed the Contractor on the eight residential blocks to undertake the new house project. Welfare facilities for the existing eight residential development were designated to be shared with the workers of the new project. The PD assisted the Client to develop a site logistics plan for the movement of persons and materials on the project site as well as between the two project sites. Such a support from the PD to the Client in this way highlights a common arrangement in the construction industry where project Clients when faced with uncertainties regarding the management of H&S risks on projects, often engage the services of other entities (i.e. CDM advisors, PDs, and H&S advisors) – competent in the management of OSH on construction projects – to assist them to fulfil their H&S duties under Regulations.

As an experienced developer, Mr Rockson led the process, appointed and entered into contracts with all other project parties (i.e. Principal Contractor, Cost Consultant, Structural Engineer, Services Engineer, Landscape Designer and Fire Engineer) independent of the PD. All of these project parties were entities Mr Rockson had engaged on previous projects. There were no rigorous processes to establish the skills, knowledge, experience (SKE) and organisational capability (OC) of the project parties regarding H&S for the project. The client simply relied on previous relationships and experiences with those parties on prior projects for appointment to the project. Such an arrangement by Mr Rockson highlights a departure from a common arrangement in the industry, in respect of getting the right people to the project with focus on H&S, where there is often a reliance on prior appointees (i.e. PD, CDM advisor, Lead Designers, and PM) already assessed for SKE/OC.

A CDM strategy brief was employed on the project as a tool for the management of H&S. Its development started upon the appointment of the PD. The deployment of this tool underlines a nascent arrangement (i.e. H&S agenda setting through client brief) by parties upstream of the construction supply chain, particularly the Client with the assistance of the PD, to provide a clear direction and expectation regarding H&S management at the outset of the project. Whereas the conventional Client brief indicates the Client requirements regarding the development of the construction project including aspirations and commitments towards H&S management, the CDM strategy brief identifies and indicates key project H&S risks at an early stage of the project development process. Further, although the process of developing the CDM strategy brief was led by the PD, inputs were often sought from appointed project participants such as Designers. In addition to identifying key H&S risks, the CDM strategy brief also indicated project milestones, pre-construction information (PCI) requirements, details of project leadership, procurement strategy, and communication strategy. An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief with these information, including the identified significant risks, are indicated in Exhibits 3a – 3c.

Organisation:

There was no specific organogram for the way H&S safety was managed on the project. Instead, a simple responsibility matrix indicating the major professional services, entities involved, and the contacts within the entities was used. This matrix was also indicated in the CDM strategy brief to provide, at a glance, useful information among project team members. This information related to entities who are responsible, accountable, may be consulted, and informed regarding certain aspects and risks related to the project. Exhibit 3c, a part of the CDM strategy brief, indicates the simple responsibility matrix for the project.

Principal CDM Documents Preparation:

Key CDM documents were developed on the project. These included the pre-construction information (PCI), construction phase plan (CPP) and H&S File (HSF).

Soon after the appointment of the Principal Designer (PD), he requested from the PM any available and relevant information or documents for the development of the project. The PM submitted information on already carried out surveys on the site to the PD and that included borehole logs and geotechnical site investigations; existing tree surveys; arboricultural assessment; and flood assessment. Upon receipt and examination of the submission, the PD developed a pre-construction information (PCI) checklist for the project. The PCI checklist requested further information such as CCTV survey of existing sewers and drainage; utilities survey regarding underground cables, gas pipes, and all live services; and party wall/boundary wall structural condition survey. Details of the PCI requirements are indicated in the excerpt of the CDM strategy brief in Exhibit 3b.

To ensure an effective communication of H&S information on the project, the PD developed a CDM report with inputs from other Designers. The CDM report included information such as the project CDM strategy brief; proposed site layout with trees conservation plan; proposed elevations with window cleaning methods, sections showing access to main roof for cleaning and maintenance; first floor with fire strategy plan; roof plan with fall restrain system for maintenance team; and hazard awareness and risk management register. Exhibits 4a – 4f indicate these information, with the exception of the hazard awareness and risk management register (HARMR). The CDM report was circulated among all dutyholders for optimal H&S decision making on the project. This arrangement of communicating PCI via a report highlights one of the modes of PCI communication in the industry in addition to other modes such as centralised information platforms, BIM tools, tender documents, and hard/USB drives.

The PD shared the PCI with the PC for the preparation of the pre-construction phase (CPP). The adequacy of the CPP was checked and approved on behalf of the Client by the Client PD upon its completion. The CDM Regulations 2015 is not quite clear on the dutyholder responsible for reviewing the quality of the CPP. Hence, its review by the PD is deemed to be a Client expectation, in the industry, as no express duty is placed on any dutyholder in this way.

In addition to supporting the preparation of the CPP, the PD supplied a template of information requirements regarding the HSF to all relevant project parties. The template was to serve as a guide in respect of what specific information and the form in which it would be required for

the purpose of the HSF. Information placed in the HSF included: as-built drawings, operation and maintenance (O&M) manuals, among others. A sample of the template is indicated in Exhibit 5.

Coordination:

Mr Adam, a conscientious PD, was committed to ensuring that all dutyholders obtained the relevant information, at the right time, to carry out their work and collaborate with each other so that the project would be carried out without risks to H&S. Hence, the PD worked with all the Designers to collate vital PCI for the development of the CDM report. Specifically, the PD developed the survey tracker to prompt the Client of required surveys, followed up on Client to commission survey teams and works. An excerpt of the survey tracker is indicated in Exhibit 6. The PD further communicated completed survey information to the design team for appropriate H&S decision making during the design process. This communication was often through the CDM reports. At design team meetings, the PD chaired and coordinated all H&S matters on the design. Further, the Designers engaged with the PCI, including the survey information, to develop their designs. Residual risks on the designs were communicated to the PD by the Designers to be populated in the HARMR which formed part of the CDM report prepared by the PD.

Four design team meetings were held in the office of the PD in Kroll before the start of the project on site. The design team meetings lasted for two hours each and had typical agenda as fire strategy, CDM issues, structural and services coordination, among others. Exhibit 7 indicates an excerpt of the agenda of a design team meeting.

At each design team meeting, the PD led the design team to identify risks with the latest versions of the design. Risks identifying prompts were mainly around buildability, usability, maintainability, and scrapping (BUMS). Solutions to the identified risks were discussed among the design team members, the risk owner was identified and a date was agreed upon to effect the solution. Each design team meeting had a recorder who captured all the decisions made at a meeting. The HARMR was updated at the end of every design team meeting. An excerpt of the HARMR is indicated in Exhibit 8. In addition to keeping a HARMR, the PD encouraged at all times, particularly at design team meetings, Designers to indicate significant residual risks on drawings for the attention of the project PC and Contractors.

Conclusions and lessons:

As the economy blossoms with attendant growth in individual wealth, the demand for domestic and private residences to meet specific lifestyles is bound to increase. Again, the locations of some of these private residential projects may be within conservation areas, as such places are often attractive to the affluent class. Hence the complexities of these private residential projects to meet certain lifestyles coupled with conservation requirements may present challenges regarding H&S risks management within the domestic market space. Hence, revisions aimed at improving future CDM Regulations must anticipate these potential challenges and make necessary considerations for them. The Rocksons family house case, thus, offers some useful

insights that may benefit future projects in respect of H&S risks management. These include the following:

- The use of a CDM reporting tool which pulls together CDM strategy information, PCI, HARMR, among other relevant information to share key project information with project participants was quite a useful one. That provided a one-stop information source for all relevant project participants. In a way, it served as a low-tech arrangement, akin to modern centralised information platforms supported by modern cloud technologies. Small to medium-scale projects can borrow this arrangement to ensure H&S information visibility and centrality among project participants.
- Sometimes, there are Clients (i.e. developers) who appear experienced in construction and may thus take over full control of arrangements on projects such as assembling the project supply chain. However, their processes may not effectively engage with H&S decisions and may ultimately undermine H&S outcomes on projects. This phenomenon may not be unique to commercial developers but also wealthy domestic Clients who may be eccentric. The eccentricism may result in such Clients insisting on the appointment of some specific team members who may be notable for certain capabilities but may be deficient in H&S competence. Therefore, appointed project participants, particularly Lead Designers, should not only possess H&S competence but also have strong negotiation skills to moderate the decisions of such Clients.
- In some cases, the officially agreed procurement strategy for the delivery of the project is deviated from and unofficial arrangements resorted to. This may be explained by poor decision making, particularly on the part of Clients, regarding the assembly of the project supply chain and weak project governance mechanisms. Such a development (i.e. deviation from official project delivery strategy) could sow seeds for potential tensions among project participants and can ultimately undermine H&S outcomes on projects. To address this challenge, project Clients, particularly domestic ones, must engage effectively with practitioners to obtain proper professional advice regarding decisions on procurement strategies.

EXHIBITS:

Exhibit 3a: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief showing key project details, milestones, and strategic risks

CDM STRATEGY BRIEF	PROJECT LEADER RESPONSES	CONTACT Nos, COMMENTS, NOTES, DATES, ETC
Project Details		
Description of Project - Outline scope of works	New build house with six bedrooms, five reception rooms and detached garden pavilion.	
Address/location/environment of site	No. 20 Creek Avenue, Kroll within the Bellevue Conservation Area	
Client Brief / Outline Scope of Work		
Operational requirements (any existing activities to remain eg. Occupation, etc.)	None	
H&S expectations of client (if above Statutory requirements)	Not above statutory requirements	
H&S file -format & index (if different to Appendix 4 L153)	As L153	
Project Timescales <i>(what are the key stages and how long will they run for?)</i>		
Concept/feasibility	August 2016 - Dec 2016	
Scheme Design/Planning	Jan 2017 - Sept 2017	
Detailed Design	Oct 2017 - Dec 2017	
Tender/selection	Jan 2018 - Mar 2018	
Construction /decommissioning	May 2018 – May 2019	
Commission/ handover/ Health & Safety File	May 2019	
Clarify at which of the above stages are you starting the CDM/Principal Designer process	Scheme Design/Planning	
Is there any pre-existing CDM Analysis, risk register or relevant information & where?	Stage 3 Report – CDM Risk Register	
Strategic Risks <i>(what are the significant or unusual H&S risks?)</i>		
Work involving Particular Risks- Refer to L153-Schedule 3	None	

Exhibit 3b: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief showing pre-construction information requirements

Project Name	Rocksons House	Project Number	22452
Building Type (new construction, refurbishment, asset management, decommissioning)	New Construction	Date of Review	XX/XX/XX
Design Stage	Stage 4	Revision no	C04

<p>Strategic Design Intent and associated risks (e.g. Major temporary works) (e.g. Stability considerations) (e.g. Unusual site constraints and logistics)</p>	<p>There are a few areas which pose a potential risk or where unknowns are present. The headlined items outlined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - B.01: Removal of all asbestos materials and contaminations - B.02, 04 and 05: narrow and deeply sloping site constrains and temporary retaining work required. Access for excavation vehicles and any other heavy machinery to be considered. - B.03: Risk of infringement of retained trees' root protection zones and canopy cover. - D.01: Risk of unknown services. - D.02: Unexpected live services extending into the site footprint and access road area. - D.03: Understanding drainage requirements of third party development towards the north of the site. - E.01: Existing obstacles and buried ordnance in the ground - H.01: Party wall and boundary wall conditions 	<p>Other structural notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Locally dewatering may be required during excavation / construction, contractor is to submit proposals for open cut excavation for review, including any temporary works required whilst forming the retaining walls. - Reduced level dig with battered sides – slope to be determined by temporary works engineer to ensure stability - A risk-based structural methodology assessment has been undertaken, backed by knowledge of existing geology and preliminary site investigations regarding buildability, hydrology, hydrogeology and land stability. Assessment indicated that the proposed development of the site should not lead to ground instability. For more information refer to ABP Structural Methodology Statement (dated November 2017)
<p>Pre-construction information requirements</p>		
<p>Pre-Construction Information -See Appendix 2 in L153-Surveys, Constraints, Planning conditions, etc)</p>	<p>Surveys carried out to date:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Borehole logs and geotechnical site investigations by KPG - Existing tree survey by KPG - Arboricultural Assessment by KPG - Flood Risk Assessment by KPG <p>Other information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural Methodology Statement by ABP - Planning Conditions Tracker by KPG 	<p>Surveys to be carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CCTV survey of existing sewers and drainage - Utilities searches required. Investigation to confirm underground cables/gas pipes and all live services. - Party wall / Boundary wall (structural) condition survey
<p>Additional Requirements for this specific Construction site Check L153 Part 4 for General Requirements</p>	<p>Works that will require specific consideration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Excavation for basement and garden pavilion -Retaining walls to neighbouring properties -Temporary works relative to the above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - See also Structural Methodology Statement by ABP

Exhibit 3c: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief showing project leadership, procurement and communication strategies

Project Name	Rocksons Fairly House	Project Number	22452
Building Type (new construction, refurbishment, asset management, decommissioning)	New Construction	Date of Review	XX/XX/XX
Design Stage	Stage 4	Revision no	C04

Project Leadership		
Client	Adrian Rockson	A.Rockson@precosh.com 06333333333
Employer Agent	Bay Consult – James Arthur	J.Arthur@precosh.com 05222222222
Principal designer	Predios Architects – Jones Adams	J.Adams@precosh.com 03444444444
Principal contractor	Falcon – Frederick Wilson	F.Wilson@precosh.com 07555555555
Cost Consultant	CSI Consult – Abraham Boye	A.Boye@precosh.com 01233333333
Structural engineer	ABP Consult – Jane Cole	J.Cole@precosh.com 020 77777777
Services engineer	Solar Engineering – Ben Hoffman	B.Hoffman@precosh.com 01523333333
Landscape designer	Greeno Ltd – Philip Baker	P.Baker@precosh.com 01852222222
Fire engineer	FM Ltd – Terry Bale	T.Bale@precosh.com 01256485555
Procurement strategy		
Contract Sum/Anticipated Project Cost	£ 2, 300, 000	
Form of Contract	Design & Build	
Communication strategy		
Team meetings anticipated, Number, frequency, length, location etc. at each workstage.	Design team meetings at stage 4	
Induction process- for new team members	CDM Report	
Visual tools, drawings, analysis documents	CDM Report, Risk Register	
Use of BIM	No	
Health and Safety File	CDM Report	

Exhibit 4a: Proposed site layout with trees conservation plan

Exhibit 4b: Proposed south elevation with window cleaning and building element maintenance approaches

Exhibit 4c: Section showing access to main roof for cleaning and maintenance

Exhibit 4d: Section showing approaches to rooflight cleaning and maintenance of pendant lights

Exhibit 4e: Proposed first floor with fire strategy plan

Exhibit 4f: Proposed roof plan with fall restrain system for maintenance team

Exhibit 5: A sample of H&S file compilation template

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Architect / Principal Designer/ Principal Contractor</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Architect, Principal Designer or the Principal Contractor, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the building fabric. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	General Materials and finishes. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	Paints / Adhesives: General type, location and COSHH data sheets where relevant for future maintenance / removal.			
	Roof Assemblies: Materials and where applicable non-fragile life.			
	Glazing: Type, weight (and location where unusual).			
	Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. cleaning of glass, gutters, external painting, include assumptions about how it could be carried out. i.e. cherry picker or long pole.			
	Provisions for future dismantling. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	"Final Construction" "As built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Civil / Structural Designer Information to be provided by the Civil / Structural Engineer, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the existing structure. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:	The basic structural form, e.g. a pin-jointed steel frame with bracing.			
	The methods of structural analysis, including the names of any computer programmes used.			
	How the characteristic loads (occupancy and environmental, e.g. wind) were derived. List the British or European standards used.			
	The wind loads: basic wind speed used and a brief résumé of how the building was defined for calculating wind coefficients.			
	How the structural elements in the structure were designed. List all standards (with their date) that were used.			
	Any deviations from the requirements in the listed standards.			
	Critical components and how they work, e.g. fixing of pre-cast walling.			
	Requirements for and provisions for future maintenance, e.g. repainting steel, resurfacing roads, etc.			
	How the calculations may be obtained, e.g. file reference numbers, location.			
	How the building could be demolished or dismantled.			
"Final Construction" "As Built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Mechanical and/or Refrigeration Designer / Engineer</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:</p>	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. temperature, heat loss / gains, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements. e.g. lifts, cranes, hoists, etc.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high pressures, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers catalogues or irrelevant information) Details to be included in the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at end of service life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Electrical Designer / Engineer Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. Illumination levels, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high voltages, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers' catalogues or irrelevant information). Details to be included in the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at end of service life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Landscape Architect / External Services Designer(s)</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Designer(s) of the External Services, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help designers to minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	The general form of the ground that the services were installed in, including any areas of significant hazard, e.g. made ground.			
	The location of services referenced from a fixed point on the building.			
	The location of isolation points within the building.			
	The depth of the services and utilities.			
	<p>For drainage runs, the following additional information would be useful;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The falls of the drains; • The length, size and unit weight of the pipes; • The location of any drains, which carry highly hazardous waste from, e.g. pathology laboratories, petrol interceptors, etc; 			
	A manhole schedule giving diameters, depths and form of access arrangements, e.g. mild steel ladders.			
	Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. Load bearing of hardstandings, lamp replacement to road lighting, etc.			
"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Principal Contractor Information to be provided by the Principal Contractor for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:	List of Subcontractors			
	List of Main Suppliers			
	O & M Manuals for Electrical, Mechanical, Refrigeration, Sprinklers, Lifts, etc. (Note: O&M Manuals to be kept as a separate document and cross referenced)			
	Product information from Nominated and Domestic Subcontractors / Suppliers relating to cleaning and maintenance of the structure, inc. COSHH data sheets where applicable.			
	Strategy for access, maintenance, cleaning, removal, renewal, de-commissioning, de-construction, demolition, etc.			
	Test Certificates / Guarantees and Warranties			
	Waste transfer documents / Air Clearance - Re-occupation Certification.			

Exhibit 6: An excerpt of the survey and data tracker

Ref	Item	Action Owner/Notes	Status
			● N/A
1	Borehole logs and geotechnical site investigations by RPS		●
2	Existing tree survey by RPS		●
3	Arboricultural assessment by RPS		●
4	Public transport accessibility level rating		N/A

Status Key

Information required/ awaiting.

N/A

Information not applicable.

Exhibit 7: An excerpt of the agenda of design team meeting

ATTENDEES		Initial
Name	Organisation	
James Arthur	Bay Consult	JA
Abraham Boye	CSI Consult	AB
Jones Adams	Predios Architects	JA
Ben Hoffman	Solar Engineering	BH
Jane Cole	ABP Consult	JC
Frank Warren	KPG	FW
MINUTES		ACTIONS
1.00	Apologies for Absence	
	FM Ltd, Terry Bale	
	Greeno Ltd, Philip Baker	
2.00	Joinery Drawings	
2.01	Predios tabled latest set of GAs and explained latest tweaks to DT.	Note
2.02	Predios to issue GA sections (PMN: issued on 14.12) to DT	Predios

3.00	Landscape Update	
3.01	Latest landscape layout by Greeno and options for boundary walls tabled for discussion	Note
3.02	Predios to send layout comments to Greeno (PMN: sent on 14.12)	PREDIOS
3.03	KPG to send comments/recommendation of boundary wall materials to Greeno/Client by 20.12	KPG
3.04	CSI to provide cost evaluation for boundary wall options by. 20.12	CSI
4.00	Planning	
4.01	KPG to update planning conditions tracker with time scales and owners by 20.09	KPG
4.02	KPG to circulate planning programme of planning conditions with references to critical path and DT/Client actions by 20.09	KPG
4.03	GREENO to issue updated landscape plan once changes have been confirmed with Client for Section 73 Submission	GREENO
4.04	SOLAR ENG. to update energy statement for smaller house for Section 73 Submission	SOLAR ENG.
4.05	ABP to provide structure statement for smaller house including reference to: demolition method statement, detailed construction method statement, site borehole logs for Section 73 Submission	ABP
4.06	PREDIOS to issue planning drawing set and design statement once the landscape changes and PV panels quantity have been confirmed for Section 73 Submission	PREDIOS

4.07	KPG note that for the purpose of the Section 73 submission, it is best to omit the two additional parking spaces underneath Atlas Cedar	Note
4.08	PREDIOS to get in contact with Arboriculturalist to clarify impact on infringement inside RPA of Sweet Chestnut tree by 20.09	PREDIOS
5.00	Fire Strategy	
5.01	KCC to assess if fire truck engine can access Creek Avenue and reach Rocksons House to determine type of fire strategy by 22.12	KCC
5.02	KCC to prepare fire strategy mark-up (including fire compartmentation and water suppression areas) by. 22.12	KCC
5.03	KCC to consider two option for first floor: one with external escape via opening window and one with motorised rooflight above staircase acting as AOV	KCC
5.04	KCC to provide type/coverage of fire alarm system	KCC
5.05	PREDIOS to issue to send KCC relevant information for fire assessment/strategy by 15.09	PREDIOS
6.00	CDM	
6.01	PREDIOS issued CDM report on 08.09	Note
6.02	DT and Client to provide feedback by 28.12	ALL
7.00	Coordination of Services and Structure	

7.01	SOLAR ENG. to provide plan of plant room showing all M&E kit by 20.12	SOLAR ENG.
7.02	SOLAR ENG. to provide update PV and solar panels area. Calculations for 2 options: one without solar coating, one with solar coating (0.53 G value) on South and West facing glazing and rooflight ABP. To be provided by 20.12	SOLAR ENG.
7.03	GREENO to indicate location of additional drainage points for external kitchen/pavilion and location of required utilities connections by 22.12	GREENO
7.04	SOLAR ENG. to provide all M&E draft schematics by 27.12	SOLAR ENG.
7.05	ABP to provide all structural draft schematics by 27.12	ABP
7.06	In latest GA mark-up (sent on 14.12) manifold on first floor is shown in cupboard, as access not possible within shower	Note
7.07	Tender Issue Deadline is on 23.01.18	Note
7.08	CSI to provide list of Client Supplied Items by 20.12.17	CSI
8.00	Date of Next Meeting 04 December, 12.30pm	Note

Exhibit 8: An excerpt of the hazard awareness and risk management register

Project Name	ROCKSONS HOUSE			Risk Tolerability/Acceptability
Project Number	22452			Work completed
Prepared by	Jones Adams	Checked by	Martin Kerr	Risk tolerable
Date	XX/XX/XX	Stage	4	Further consideration required
				Risk not tolerable

Risk Ref.	Relevant Hazard / Risk Identification	Design Control Measures / Residual Risk / Drg. Ref.	Action Owner	Date Required	Completed
B.01-Client	Demolition of existing structures onsite	Site clearance certificate required to demonstrate all asbestos materials / contaminations (if any) have been removed.	Client	Before site works begin	NO
B.02-Phase 01	Access and crange on narrow sloping site	Coordination with Ridge House School development can allow easier access to Rocksons House site with safer execution of structural works.	SE with Design Team / Phase 01 Contractor	Before site works begin	Phase 01 Work complete
B.02-Phase 02	Access and crange on narrow sloping site	Coordination with Ridge House School development can allow easier access to Rocksons House site with safer execution of works. *Construction Phase Plan and Safety File required	Design Team / Main Contractor	Before site works begin	Yes
B.03-Phase 01	Protection to retained trees	To ensure when any large vehicle access occur, all retained tree root protection areas are respected to avoid killing trees or causing damage to structures, vehicles and injuries to people. *See also construction advice set in the Arboricultural Assessment.	Design Team / Phase 01 Contractor	Before site works begin	Phase 01 Work complete
B.03-Phase 02	Protection to retained trees	To ensure when any large vehicle access occur, all retained tree root protection areas are respected to avoid killing trees or causing damage to structures, vehicles and injuries to people. *See also construction advice set in the Arboricultural Assessment.	Design Team / Main Contractor	Before site works begin	Yes (exclusion zone set-up)
B.04-Phaes 01	Open-cut excavations for basement and retaining walls with temporary structural condition.	Phase 01 contractor shall refer to Structural Methodology Statement by SE and submit proposal including temporary structural works. All info submitted to be reviewed by SE. *Local dewatering may be required.	SE / Phase 01 Contractor	Before site works begin	Phase 01 Work complete
B.05-Phase 01	Welfare facilities and vehicle off-loading area on a sloping site	Coordination with Ridge House School development can allow for combined welfare facilities and off-loading area.	Client / Phase 01 Contractor	Before site works begin	Phase 01 Work complete
B.05-Phase 02	Welfare facilities and vehicle off-loading area on a	Coordination with Ridge House School development can allow for	Client / Main	Before site	Yes